

Effectiveness Of Monitoring And Evaluation System In Federal Government Secondary Schools and Use Of Information Communication Technology As A National Professional Standard For Teachers In Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Effectiveness, Monitoring and Evaluation, National Professional Standard, Information and Communication Technology, Secondary School Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4990010</p>	<p><i>The study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation system on performance of secondary school teachers (SSTs) in Information Communication Technology (ICT) usage. The study was conducted in 188 secondary schools of Directorate of Federal Government Educational Institutions Rawalpindi. The performance levels of 269 Secondary Schools Teachers were observed by 134 Principals, 19 Conveners and also data were collected from 349 Secondary School Teachers seeking their opinions about their own performance regarding use of ICT. The performance of SSTs was observed before and after implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation System in use of ICT as a national professional standard for teachers in Pakistan, therefore, it was an ex post facto causal comparative study by design. because. Mixed method was used to triangulate the data. To find out the effectiveness of Use of ICT, rating scales for Principals, rating scale Secondary School Teachers, and interview schedule for Conveners were used. On the other hand, the performance of SSTs was observed by the document analysis. Stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample from all areas/regions/sex of Pakistan. Paired tailed t-tests were used to analyze the data. The improvement in performance of SSTs in use of ICT was found after implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation System.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is comprised of computers, the Internet electronic delivery systems as radios, televisions, and projectors among others. Now a days ICT is widely used in the field of education. Kent and Facer (2004) pointed out that school is an important environment in which students participate in a multi range of computer activities, while the home serves as a complementary site for regular engagement in a narrower set of computer activities. Chien, Wu and Hsu (2014) found that students in schools are having high expectations on ICT integration in classrooms as the new generation are born and grown with sources of technologies and can be considered as the digital. According to Chen (2010), Wong, Teo & Russo (2012) it is imperative to study the way ICT is used in schools and to identify the factors that contribute to teachers' use of ICT. ICT is considered as a performance standard for school teachers. The use of ICT in schools as a professional standard has become growing aspect of performance. Internationally, many governments and regulatory bodies pursue to ensure the preparation, readiness, and viewing performance of teachers through the accreditation policies and implementation of professional standards. Widely reported standardization of education has also shown the desired effect on teachers, schools, and classrooms (Bourke, 2011; Bourke, Ryan, & Lidstone, 2012; Clarke & Moore, 2013; Darling-Hammond, 2001; Ingvarson, 2010; Marrongelle, Sztajn, & Smith, 2013; NíChróinín, Tormey, & O'Sullivan, 2012; Polikoff, 2013; Taubman, 2009).

As mentioned in recent studies on professional standards, rather to identify types or discourses of standards, the key concerning point is arguing for a degree of caution about implementation of professional standards (Bourke, 2011; Bourke et al., 2012; Clarke & Moore, 2013; NíChróinín et al., 2012; Tang, Cheng, & So, 2006). Regardless of how standards are observed in schools, their promulgation and implementation continue both in schools and, is taken more considered as an important aspect in teaching learning process. Professional standards improve teaching quality in schools.

Use of ICT brought imperative academic and instructional change. According to Roberts (2003) and Gonzalez (2010) currently, ICT plays a vital role in promoting new instructional methods for teaching and learning, such as: self-paced learning, network learning and online discussion. Moreover, effective use of ICT can facilitates student-centered active learning culture (Ellis et al., 2008). It engages students in collaborative learning as well as enhance their social interaction (Dodge et al., 2003). According to Danielson, McGreal (2000) & Darling-

Hammond (2001) professional standards for teachers are considered, developed and implemented globally in different shapes and they are justified by an argument that they improve the quality of teaching and in turn raise students' outcomes.

Use of ICT, as a National Professional Standard, proved its effectiveness in improving secondary school teachers' teaching quality. As Yusuf (2005) rightly supported that the field of education has been affected by ICT, which has definitely affected teaching, learning, and research. Further added by Al-Ansari (2006) that a great deal of research proved the benefits to the quality of education. According to Davis and Tearle (1999), Lemke and Coughlin (1998), cited by Yusuf (2005) ICTs have the ability to innovate, accelerate, enrich, and deepen skills, to motivate and engage students, to relate school experience to work practices, create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, as well as strengthening teaching and helping schools change. As per point of view of Flecknoe (2002), McCormick & Scrimshaw (2001), Garrison & Anderson (2003) ICT is proving a catalyst for rethinking teaching practice. According to Kozma (2005), Kulik (2003), Webb & Cox (2004) ICT helps students deepening their content knowledge, makes them able to construct their own knowledge, and supports the development of complex thinking skills. Rienstra (2010) said that as in Australia in 2011, after a process of consultation with stakeholders across all regional jurisdictions, Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (AITSL) introduced the Australian Professional Standards for Teachers (APST).

The National Education Policy (2009) is the first document of Pakistan which also articulated the strong need for applying standards-based education system in the country. The said policy asserts "to improve quality education in government institutions would be possible by designing the professional standards for educational inputs, processes, outputs and also institutionalizing the process of monitoring and evaluation ranging from bottom to top". Federal Ministry of Education of Pakistan in accordance with the guidance of the National Education Policy 2009 initially introduced ten National Professional Standards for Teachers in Pakistan, in which Effective use of ICT is one. Doubtlessly, use of ICT by the teachers was a need of time. As Senanayake (2009) states that even though finding effectiveness of a system is a challenge. It is a challenging aspect for evaluation to gauge the effectiveness. In this way its use and then monitoring and evaluation of its effectiveness both were the challenging tasks for school/educational administrations working in all over Pakistan. So, there was a need of an independent Monitoring and Evaluation System as Du Plessis (2013) explained that monitoring of process of teaching and learning mainly provides sort of effective feedback which may further lead to start specific professional development efforts to enhance performance levels. According to Briceno (2009), independent Monitoring and Evaluation (M & E) System makes it trustable and dependable, so it is necessary, a viable and M & E System must be independent enough to be externally reliable and socially legitimate.

Therefore, the Directorate of Federal Government Educational Institutions Rawalpindi introduced its Monitoring and Evaluation System, and this task was assigned to this system. Use of ICT as National Professional Standard for Teachers is exercised in 189 Federal Government Secondary Schools (all over Pakistan) run by the Directorate of Federal Government Educational Institutions Rawalpindi and monitored by the Monitoring & Evaluation System of this Directorate. This study was conducted to gauge the effectiveness of ICT (as a National Professional Standard for Teachers) used in teaching learning process by the Secondary School Teachers, which on the other hand, was the analysis of performance of M&E System launched the Directorate of Federal Government Educational Institutions Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Objectives of the Study

Following were the objectives of the study

- i. To evaluate the effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation system in Federal Government secondary schools
- ii. To assess the effectiveness of ICT used in Federal Government secondary schools

Research Hypothesis

Following hypotheses were tested in the study

- i. H₁: There is no effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation system observed on the performance of SSTs in use of ICT.
- ii. H₂: There is no effectiveness of use of ICT in teaching learning process at secondary school level.

Research Methodology

It was an ex-post facto causal-comparative study by design. Effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation System (M&E) and use of ICT in Federal Government Schools were found. It was observed by comparing the performance levels before and after implementation of M & E. Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) as a cause, an independent variable and its effect on dependent variables i.e. performance of Secondary School Teachers (SSTs) in Use of ICT as a National professional standard for teachers in Pakistan was assessed. The performance of SSTs was observed before and after implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation system.

Population of the Study

It was comprised of 188 Secondary School Principals (SSPs), 1788 Secondary School Teachers (SSTs) and 19 Conveners of Quality Audit Team.

Sample and Sampling

Stratified sample of 133 secondary school male / female Principals, 248 secondary school male / female teachers and 19 male / female conveners were taken from 4 provinces of Pakistan.

Research Instruments

As per following detail four research instruments were designed after review of the related literature.

- i. A five point Likert scale comprising 28 items for Secondary School Principals was developed to collect the data about the performance of Secondary School Teachers in use of ICT before and after implementation of monitoring and evaluation system.
- ii. Another five point Likert scale comprising 27 items for Secondary School Teachers was developed to find self-opinion about their own performance before and after implementation of monitoring and evaluation system.
- iii. An interview schedule was designed to seek opinion from Conveners of Quality Audit Teams (as third group of sample) to collect the data.

Validation and Pilot Testing of Research Instruments

These research instruments were validated by the 12 experts of the field of education. In the light of their comments and input instruments, few items were dropped and remaining were improved. Instruments were pilot tested. Pilot test was conducted on N=25 Teachers, Principals N=20 and Conveners N= 5. Reliability alpha value for Rating Scale for Principal 0.953, Rating scale for secondary school teachers 0.977, it determined significant Cronbach alpha value, Moreover skewness and kurtosis of tools were calculated which falls less than 1, it determined significant Cronbach alpha value in this context.

Data Collection

The researchers approached the Directorate of Federal Government Educational Institutions, situated in Rawalpindi Saddar and collected the addresses, locations, contact numbers and email IDs of all sample groups on special request. Therefore, data were collected personally by the researchers from approachable areas, whereas, data from distant areas were collected through emails. The response rate was 92 percent.

Data Analysis

In this study, data was collected through three Rating Scales, an interview schedule and document analysis. Then it was tabulated and as well as decoded as per five point Likert scale i.e. strongly agree: 5 score, agree: 4 scores, neutral: 3 marks, disagree: 2 scores and disagree: 1 score. To assess the effectiveness of professional standard Use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) before and after implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation system, two tailed t test at 0.05 alpha value was used to find comparison of two means. Moreover, document analysis (Thematic analysis) of audit reports and academic results of secondary schools were done to find application and effectiveness of use of information and communication technology. Triangulation of results by analyzing the qualitative and quantitative data was made. According to Morse and Niehaus (2009) and Guest (2013), each true mixed methods study contains at least one "point of integration" that is called the "point of interface", at this stage qualitative and quantitative components are brought together. Following data analysis was made to find the point of integration or congruence and new exploration.

Data presentation and interpretation of Secondary School Principals' results

H₁ There is no effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation system observed on the performance of SSTs in use of ICT

Table: The performance of secondary school teachers (SSTs) as it is observed by their Principals in Use of Information and Communication Technologies before & after implementation of M&E.

Category	Before implementation of M&E			After implementation of M&E			t
	f	%age	Mean	F	%age	Mean	
Standard use of ICT Technologies	SA	32	12	125	46		
	Agree	126	47	111	41		
	UD	68	25	3.50	19	7	4.27
	DA	35	13		11	4	29.652
	SDA	9	3		4	1	

SA (Strongly Agree) =5, Agree=4, UD (Undecided) =3, DA (Disagree) =2, SDA (Strongly Disagree) =1, N=269

As per above table, performance of secondary school teachers (SSTs) is improved After implementation of monitoring & evaluation (M&E) system as per Mean value is = 4.27 which is found better than their performance before implementation of monitoring & evaluation (M&E) system as per Mean value is = 3.50.

Calculated t value is $t(269) = 29.652$ which lies in rejection region on $\alpha = 0.05$ as quite higher than table value that is 1.968, therefore Null Hypothesis H_0 is rejected, Hence there is significant difference in the performance of SSTs after implementation of Monitoring and evaluation (ME) in the standard use of ICT in classrooms that shows the effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation system.

H₂ There is no effectiveness of use of ICT in teaching learning process at secondary school level.

Table 2: *The performance of Secondary school teachers (SSTs) as per their self- opinions to find the effectiveness of Use of Information and Communication Technologies before & after implementation of Monitoring & Evaluation system in Federal Government secondary schools*

	Category	Before implementation of M&E			After implementation of M&E			t
		F	%age	Mean	f	%age	Mean	
Standard use of ICT technologies	SA	58	22		197	73		
	Agree	182	67		120	45		
	UD	68	25	3.72	21	8	4.41	31.760
	DA	36	13		4	2		
	SDA	6	2		8	3		

SA (Strongly Agree) =5, Agree=4, UD (Undecided) =3, DA (Disagree) =2, SDA (Strongly Disagree) =1, N=349

As per above table according to their own opinions, the performance of SSTs is improved after implementation of monitoring & evaluation (M&E) system as Mean value is = 4.41 is found better than the performance of secondary school teachers before implementation of monitoring & evaluation (M&E) system as per Mean value is =3.72.

Calculated t value is $t(349) = 31.760$ that is found in rejection region on $\alpha = 0.05$ quite higher than table value that is 1.968, therefore Null Hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there exists significant difference in performance of Secondary School Teachers in use of ICT after implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation system.

Data presentation and interpretation of Interviews of Conveners' results

As per thematic analysis of interviews of 19 Conveners of quality audit teams, it was reflected mixed opinions as a result of integration. As per Conveners, 48 % secondary school teachers used Information and Communication Technologies effectively in their teaching learning process.

However, 21 % secondary school teachers remained neutral and 31 % are of opinion that they do not use information and communication technology during teaching. Even 48% shows of secondary school teachers follow Use of Information and Communication Technologies in teaching but equally 52% (21 % & 31%) are not favoring the use of ICT. It indicated that there is need to improve the provision of ICT gadgets and capacity building of teachers in schools.

Data presentation and interpretation of Quality Audit Reports' results

Quality Audit reports and academic results supported the effectiveness of Use of Information and Communication Technologies of secondary school teachers as academic results of secondary schools raised (GPA raised from 3.30 to 4.53) after implementation of Monitoring and evaluation system standard of use of ICT in secondary schools. It also reflected the effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation system.

Conclusions

1. The performance of secondary school teachers improved in use of ICT after implementation of Monitoring and evaluation system as observed by Principals.
2. Secondary school teachers viewed their own performance improved by using ICT
3. Improvement in academic results after introduction of Monitoring and evaluation system shows its effectiveness and effective use of ICT by SSTs.
4. As per qualitative analysis of interviews of Conveners SSTs have no adequate ICT facilities and gadgets in schools.

Discussion

This study proved that effective application of ICT became part of positive change in secondary school teacher's performance. The research conducted by Shamim Huq and Abu Raihan (2015) in Bangladesh also supported that most of the teachers possess knowledge about using ICTs in teaching and learning. Majority of the respondents were in favour of arrangement of adequate ICTs for classroom teaching. According to Ghavifekr, Afshari & Amla Salleh, (2012), as now a part of this, schools and other similar educational institutions which are

set to prepare students to live in “a knowledge society” need to keep ICT integration in their curriculum. The results of this study indicated that ICT integration in education generally termed as technology-based teaching and learning process that relates to the utilization of learning technologies in schools. . Monitoring and Evaluation is key system through which effectiveness of use of ICT may be gauged as performance standard. Danielson (2001) supported that Monitoring and Evaluation system has extensive range of goals and objectives related NPSTs, but the leading goal is that is to ensure the quality of the teaching process in schools.

The outcomes of Monitoring and Evaluation shows that due to the fact that students are familiar with technology and they may learn better with help of technology-based environment, the issue of ICT integration in schools which is vital for classroom. Whereas the improvement in academic results shows the students success rate is due to that instructional variety i.e. use of this professional standard (ICT) by the teachers. GPA of secondary schools raised from 3.30 to 4.53 As per Borich (2000), the responsibilities of effective teachers show lesson clarity, instructional variety, engagement students in the learning process and student success rate. This study also proved that by the use of information and communication technology as a variety brought academic results up of students.

The conclusions of the study show the improvement in secondary school performance, it approves the use of technology in education contributes a lot in the pedagogical aspects of teachers in which the application of ICT may lead to effective learning. As Zhang & Aikman (2007) opined that use of Information and communication technology is an inevitable part of most of the institution these days. It is due with the help and supports from ICT elements and components (Jamieson-Procter et al., 2013). As a result, as per to Bond & Peterson (2004), planning and proactive strategies of teachers improve success level of class and shows effective outcomes. The system of Monitoring and evaluation system brought about the weaknesses and strength of the performance standard teaching of different subjects through use of information and communication technology which ultimately improved the learning rate. According to Jorge et al (2003), in almost all types of subjects’ as mathematics, science, languages, arts and humanistic and other major fields may be learned more effectively through technology-based tools and equipment. Moreover, ICT helps and complementary supports for both teachers and students where it involves effective learning with the help of the computers to serve the purpose of learning aids.

ICT use improves the learning level of students which improved students’ academic results , GPA of Federal Government secondary schools improved from 3.30 to 4.53 . As supported by Cox et al. (2004) reported on a positive relationship of the use of ICT and students learning of specific math concepts and skills. Secondary school teachers found it effective as Monitoring and Evaluation results indicated in this study. As mentioned in the study conducted by Tazci (2011) that most of pre-service teachers indicated that they only involve elementary ICT tools for educational use, most teachers think ICT integration is effective. However, ICT tools provided in schools are not enough nor in good condition; professional development is not adequately provided for teachers.

The 50 % opinions of Conveners about teachers use of ICT is found positive but remaining 50% did not support the use of ICT. It means that 50 % teachers are not provided the ICT facilities in classrooms and not enough trained to use these facilities. As per research of Mulhim (2013) in which he found that teachers’ low level of ICT usage is due to lack of relevant training. Another worldwide survey conducted by Pelgrum (2001), of nationally representative samples of schools from 26 countries which further supported that teachers’ lack of knowledge and skills is a serious obstacle to using ICT in primary and secondary schools. This result suggested an urgent need to train teachers in pedagogical and technical skills to use ICT in schools. According to Wilson et al., 2001 , the level of teachers education and preparation in the subject they teach directly correlate positively with students’ academic achievements if teachers competent and confident in use of ICT, researchers (Aslan & Zhu, 2017) found that ICT confidence and ICT competence depends upon teachers’ integration of ICT into their teaching.

Recommendations

1. Secondary school teachers’ performance showed significant improvement, it emphasizes the need to introduce Monitoring and Evaluation System at primary, middle and college level too.
2. Manual collection of information and data for evaluation of SSTs performance took fair amount of time and resources. Therefore, there is a need to introduce Monitoring and Evaluation software for this purpose to save money and time.
3. SSTs used ICT with alternate resources and attained significant improvement but basic standard of ICT equipment’ and gadgets were not provided, need to equip classrooms and faculty with basic ICT facilities.
4. Training of all levels of teachers for effective use of ICT gadgets is also recommended, which may be launched by the Directorate of Education.

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